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UPDATES ON GENUS *ACONITUM* IN GORGANY MTS

Introduction

Gorgany Mts. is one of the biggest regions of Ukrainian Carpathians expanded on about 4224 sq. km, and divided onto 8 main subregions including Zaprutski Gorgany, Svitsko-Mizunski Gorgany, Dovbushanski Gorgany, Arshytisia-Ilemski Gorgany, Verkhniolimnytski Gorgany, Syvuliansko-Stanymyrski Gorgany, Torunsko-Bertianski Gorgany, and Bratkiivski Gorgany (Fig. 1.). Gorgany Mts. are located in central part of Ukrainian Carpathians, and predominantly consist of shales and sandstones (Kravchuk, 2005). This is one of 4 regions of Ukrainian Carpathians where alpine belt is represented, what together with huge forest covering (up to 1600 m a.s.l.) makes it unique and hard for travel. Gorgany Mts. have relict forests and number of unique plant communities, scattering mostly in alpine and subalpine belts. In general, here are represented about 17 % of rare and relict plants of Ukrainian Carpathians, including about 30 plant species protected by Red Book of Ukraine and at least 25 endemic taxa (Klimuk et al., 2006).

Fig. 1. Geomorphological division of Gorgany Mts. following Novikov & Hurdu (2017), with recent updates made by Novikov.

For Gorgany Mts. only 7 *Aconitum* species (*A. bucovinense*, *A. firmum*, *A. nanum*, *A. lasiocarpum*, *A. degenii*, *A. moldavicum*, and *A. variegatum*) were mentioned for long time (Klimuk et al., 2006; Mitka, 2003, 2008). However, my previous studies in 2011 revealed at least 9 *Aconitum* taxa for this region (including rare hybrids *A. × czarnohorensse* and *A. × nanum*) and did not confirm presence here of *A. variegatum* (Novikoff, 2011; Novikoff, Mitka, 2011). From this number, 7 taxa are endemics/subendemics, and 5 considered belonging to VU or EN categories (Novikoff et al., 2016). Unfortunately, due the lack of data on genus taxonomy, distribution and population conditions, among mentioned taxa only *A. lasiocarpum* was included in the last edition of the Red Book of Ukraine in 2009 (Didukh, 2009). Hence, my current aim was to investigate taxonomical diversity and spatial distribution of monkshoods in Gorgany Mts. with perspective of evaluation of threats and categorization following IUCN criteria.

Material and methods

Field investigations were made during July–August 2018. Totally I have discovered and evaluated 22 localities with aconites in Gorgany Mts. For all of them the population parameters, ecological conditions, vegetation structure and classification were realized and databased. This data allowed evaluating the general condition and threats of aconites in Gorgany. Threat categories for all investigated taxa were provided in accordance to IUCN criteria (IUCN 2012).

After that data gathered in field were combined with those obtained during previous studies in 2011 and those obtained from published sources, including printed materials, webservices and databases (Fig. 2). As a result, consolidated dataset in DarwinCore format was developed and later processed within QGIS 3.10.2 environment. Maps were built with EPSG:3857 Pseudomercator projection.

Fig. 2. Distribution of genus *Aconitum* in Gorgany Mts. by the type of data source.

Results and discussion

My research confirmed presence of 12 instead of suggested 9 taxa of the genus *Aconitum* in Gorgany region (Table 1; Figs. 3–5). Presence of two other species mentioned in publications for the Gorgany Mts. (*A. anthora* and *A. variegatum*) was not confirmed. Moreover, during my field trips I have found specific population of *A. lasiocarpum* with gemmules and wild individuals of *A. × cammarum* that probably were before treated as *A. variegatum*, so this can explain numerous wrong citations of *A. variegatum* from Gorgany. After analysis of scattering of observed locations between different regions, I also found that Torunsko–Bertianski Gorgany are the most rich on monkshoods and represent 76 known locations. Syvuliansko–Stanymyrski and Dovbushanski Gorgany are also quite rich and include 60 known localities of monkshoods each. Mesoregion of Zaprutski Gorgany contains only 5 documented localities (Fig. 6). However, I cannot surely that this is due to low occurrence of *Aconitum* in this region. Zaprutski Gorgany are definitely not reach on monkshoods, but, together with Svitchsko–Mezunski Gorgany, they are among the poorest investigated regions. For example, in Zaprutski Gorgany is growing *A. × gayeri*, however no any known location of more widely distributed *A. degenii* that should be represented here too. Here also no any evidence of presence of *A. moldavicum* subsp. *hosteanum*, which usually grow in such habitats. I also tried to analyze species richness of different Gorgany mesoregions and found that Torunsko–Bertianski and Syvuliansko–Stanymyrski Gorgany are the richest and represent 9 taxa each. Arshytisia–Ilemski and Verkhniolimytski Gorgany also quite diverse and represent 7 *Aconitum* taxa each (Fig. 7). And still, Zaprutski and Svitchsko–Mezunski Gorgany are the poorest on *Aconitum* taxa.

Table 1. List of *Aconitum* taxa investigated for Gorgany Mts., their endemicity and threat categories.

Taxon	Threat category	Endemic status
Subgen. <i>Aconitum</i>		
Sect. <i>Aconitum</i>		
<i>A. × czarnohorensis</i> (Zapat.) Mitka	VU	Eastern Carpathian endemic
<i>A. × nanum</i> (Baumg.) Simonk.	VU	South–Eastern Carpathian endemic
<i>A. bucovinense</i> Zapat.	EN	South–Eastern Carpathian endemic
<i>A. firmum</i> Rchb. subsp. <i>fissurata</i> Nyárády	VU	Pan–Carpathian endemic
Sect. <i>Cammarum</i> DC.		
<i>A. lasiocarpum</i> (Rchb.) Gáyer subsp. <i>lasiocarpum</i>	VU	Eastern Carpathian endemic
<i>A. lasiocarpum</i> (Rchb.) Gáyer subsp. <i>kotulae</i> (Pawł.) Starmühl. & Mitka	VU	Pan–Carpathian subendemic
<i>A. × gayeri</i> Starmühl.	LC	Eastern Carpathian endemic
<i>A. degenii</i> Gáyer subsp. <i>degenii</i> fo. <i>degenii</i>	LC	Pan–Carpathian endemic
<i>A. degenii</i> Gáyer subsp. <i>degenii</i> var. <i>intermedium</i> (Zapat.) Mitka	LC	Pan–Carpathian endemic
Sect. <i>Acomarum</i> Starmühl.		
<i>A. × cammarum</i> L. em. Fries	LC	none
Subgen. <i>Lycotconum</i> (DC.) Peterm.		
Sect <i>Lycotconum</i> DC.		
<i>A. moldavicum</i> Hacq. subsp. <i>moldavicum</i>	LC	Pan–Carpathian subendemic
<i>A. moldavicum</i> Hacq. subsp. <i>hosteanum</i> (Schur) Graebn. & P. Graebn.	LC	Pan–Carpathian endemic

Fig. 3. Distribution of *Aconitum* sect. *Aconitum*, and supposed but not confirmed location of *A. anthora* in Gorgany Mts.

Fig. 4. Distribution of *Aconitum* sect. *Cammarum* in Gorgany Mts.

Fig. 5. Distribution of *Aconitum* subgen. *Lycoctonum* in Gorgany Mts.

Fig. 6. Occurrence richness of *Aconitum* in different Gorgany regions. The higher intensity of color the higher number of observed localities.

Fig. 7. Taxa diversity of *Aconitum* in different Gorgany regions. The higher intensity of color the higher number of observed localities.

I did not find some special associations representing monkshoods in Gorgany Mts. These plants take a part in many different plant communities and in many cases they have no special preferences different from those described for other Carpathian regions. For example, one of the most abundant species *A. degenii* in Gorgany Mts. can participate in 8 different associations (*Adenostyletum alliariae*, *Ranunculo platanifolii-Adenostyletum alliariae*, *Fagion sylvaticae*, *Rubetum idaei*, *Caricetum brizoidis*, *Arunco-Doronicetum austriaci*, *Stellario nemorum – Alnetum glutinosa*, and *Chaerophylletum aromaticum*), while *A. moldavicum* occur in 6 associations (*Adenostyletum alliariae*, *Fagion sylvaticae*, *Rubetum idaei*, *Arunco – Doronicetum austriaci*, *Stellario nemorum – Alnetum glutinosa*, and *Chaerophylletum aromaticum*). So, I can conclude that associations are not limiting the distribution of monkshoods in the Gorgany Mts., either we need to provide different kind of analysis.

For all localities I analyzed suppressing factors and found that main of them in this region are deforestation, trampling by tourists, destruction by locals, and overgrowing by shrubs.

Conclusions

All taxa of the genus *Aconitum* were evaluated in accordance with IUCN criteria on the base of newly obtained information. The maps of distribution for all discovered taxa were prepared, and now it is much easy to realize further biogeographical studies in this region. Torunsko-Bertianski and Syvuliansko-Stanymyrski Gorgany seems to be the most divers and reach on *Aconitum*. Despite the fact that Zaprutski and Svitschsko-Mezunski Gorgany are quite poor on *Aconitum*, however these regions also suffer from lack of data and require further field investigations. I also can assume that *A. variegatum* and *A. anthora* most probably are not growing in the Gorgany Mts.

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Моніторинг та охорона біорізноманіття в Україні

Рослинний світ та гриби

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Рослинний світ та гриби

Том 1

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